

A micrometer-scale snapshot on phototroph spatial distributions: mass spectrometry imaging of microbial mats in Octopus Spring, Yellowstone National Park

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Abstract

Microbial mats from alkaline hot springs in the Yellowstone National Park are ideal natural laboratories to study photosynthetic life under extreme conditions, as well as the nuanced interactions of oxygenic and anoxygenic phototrophs. They represent distinctive examples of chlorophototroph (i.e., chlorophyll or bacteriochlorophyll-based phototroph) diversity, and several novel phototrophs have been first described in these systems, all confined in space, coexisting and competing for niches defined by parameters such as light, oxygen, or temperature. In a novel approach, we employed mass spectrometry imaging of chloropigments, quinones, and intact polar lipids (IPLs) to describe the spatial distribution of different groups of chlorophototrophs along the ~ 1 cm thick microbial mat at 75 μm resolution and in the top ~ 1.5 mm green part of the mat at 25 μm resolution. We observed a fine-tuned sequence of oxygenic and anoxygenic chlorophototrophs with distinctive biomarker signatures populating the microbial mat. The transition of oxic to anoxic conditions is characterized by an accumulation of biomarkers indicative of anoxygenic phototrophy. It is also identified as a clear boundary for different species and ecotypes, which adjust their biomarker inventory, particularly the interplay of quinones and chloropigments, to prevailing conditions. Colocalization of the different biomarker groups led to the identification of characteristic IPL signatures and indicates that glycosidic diether glycerolipids are diagnostic for anoxygenic phototrophs in this mat system. The zoom-in into the upper green part further reveals how oxygenic and anoxygenic phototrophs share this microenvironment and informs on subtle, microscale adjustments in lipid composition of *Synechococcus* spp.

KEYWORDS

intact polar lipids, MALDI FT-ICR-MS, microbial mat, molecular biomarker, *Roseiflexus*, *Synechococcus*

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1 | INTRODUCTION

Microbial mats are finely structured, multi-layered, self-sustaining ecosystems that contain assemblages of distinct microbial populations intercalated by an organic matrix and mineral precipitates. They develop at the sediment/water interface, and thrive in a variety of habitats, especially in those representing extremes in pH, temperature, or salinity that preclude or inhibit metazoan grazing. Their internal organization responds to sharp gradients of physical and chemical parameters, for example, quantity and quality of light and O_2 concentration, which can transition from supersaturation to anoxia within millimeters or less (Franks & Stolz, 2009). Prerequisites for the growth and persistence of microbial mats include relatively stable conditions over a sufficient period of time to allow establishment of vertical lamination and the absence of grazing fauna (Fenchel, 1998). Modern microbial mat systems are useful as models for microbial ecology and as natural laboratories for fine-scale microbial interactions and adaptations, but also as analogs of Precambrian ecosystems (Des Marais, 2003). The widespread preservation of microbial mats in the rock record signifies their importance as witnesses of early Earth; microbial mats are considered as the oldest known ecosystem (Allwood et al., 2009; Allwood, Walter, Kamber, Marshall, & Burch, 2006; Noffke, Christian, Wacey, & Hazen, 2013).

In the Yellowstone National Park (YNP), microbial mats develop at the outflow channels of hydrothermal springs. The phototrophic mats from the hot, alkaline, low sulfide Octopus Spring (OS), and Mushroom Spring (MS) have been used as model systems for microbial ecology at the upper temperature limits of photosynthesis for decades (Bolhuis, Cretoiu, & Stal, 2014 and references therein). While these systems were initially deemed to be rather simple, we now know that they present an extraordinary diversity of chlorophototrophs. So far, representatives of six of the seven chlorophototroph phyla have been detected in OS and MS (Tank, Thiel, Ward, & Bryant, 2017). Moreover, chlorophototrophs from the phyla Chloroflexi and Acidobacteria were first isolated from these systems (Bryant et al., 2007; Pierson & Castenholz, 1974).

The blueish-green top part of these mats (Figure 1a) is dominated by densely growing unicellular *Synechococcus* spp. (Cyanobacteria) that serve as the main primary producers in the mat, fueling the system through oxygenic photosynthesis and nitrogen fixation (Steunou et al., 2006). Chloroflexi are also abundant and include well-known filamentous anoxygenic phototrophs (FAPs) of the genera *Chloroflexus* and *Roseiflexus*, as well as the previously unknown chlorophototroph "*Ca. Roseilinea gracile*" (Klatt et al., 2011; Nubel et al., 2002; Pierson & Castenholz, 1974; Tank et al., 2017; Thiel et al., 2016; van der Meer et al., 2010). In the investigated microbial mats, FAPs grow photo- or chemoheterotrophically on cyanobacterial products. Photoautotrophic or mixotrophic growth also takes place, especially at dawn and dusk, when light and the electron donors H_2 and H_2S are available (Klatt et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2011; van der Meer et al., 2005). The additional presence of novel, rather unusual aerobic photoheterotrophs from the phyla Chlorobi ("*Ca. Thermochlorobacter aerophilum*") and Acidobacteria (*Chloracidobacterium thermophilum*), has been confirmed in the last decade (Bryant et al., 2007; Klatt et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2012).

Several studies further point to the existence of a "hidden higher microdiversity" (Bolhuis et al., 2014) in the form of ecotypes (i.e., a subset of individuals within a species with a characteristic ecology (Begon, Harper, & Townsend, 1986)). The *Synechococcus* spp. population, for example, has been described to consist of several ecotypes, which due to their different physiological traits are able to populate distinct habitats associated to specific light, temperature and nutrient regimes (Ferris, Kuhl, Wieland, & Ward, 2003; Ramsing, Ferris, & Ward, 2000; Ward et al., 2006).

The microbial, red- or orange-colored, undermat (located below the 1–2 mm thick upper green part, Figure 1a) has been less studied. Metagenomic analyses of the MS undermat (Thiel et al., 2016) revealed a higher diversity, with at least 44 abundant taxa resulting from a diverse assemblage of aerobic, anaerobic, and microaerobic organisms with photo- and chemotrophic lifestyles (Thiel, Hugler, Ward, & Bryant, 2017). A highly diverse assemblage of *Roseiflexus* spp. ecotypes was the dominant members of the undermat. Interestingly,

FIGURE 1 Pictures of (a) the embedded microbial mat from Octopus Spring and (b) a 100- μ m thick slice, overlaid with a representation of the two MSI measurement regions (white lines) and Fe abundance (black) obtained from elemental mapping. Only Fe abundances above the 50th percentile are shown for better visualization. The prominent Fe band is tentatively interpreted as the oxic-anoxic transition zone (OATZ) and represented as a dotted gray line in the measurement region. The green and two different red layers that were subsampled for conventional analysis can be distinguished in Figure 1a

all chlorophototrophs identified in the upper green part were also detected in the undermat metagenome, together with an additional FAP: the anaerobic photoheterotroph "*Ca. Chloranaerofilum corporosum*" (Thiel et al., 2016).

Lipid biomarkers derived from microbial cell membrane constituents account for chemotaxonomic diversity and also record-specific signatures of processes or environmental conditions. As a result, they provide complementary information to genetic or genomic techniques. In streamer biofilm communities from hot springs in the YNP, Schubotz et al. (2013, 2015) employed the structural diversity of intact polar lipids (IPLs) as a chemotaxonomic tool and the isotopic compositions of their breakdown products as indicators of metabolic pathways. Thereby, they identified many of the microbial mat communities to be mixotrophic and reliant on exogenous carbon sources. Molecular biomarkers also have the potential to persist over geological timescales and thus to inform on microbial communities through time (Brocks & Summons, 2005).

However, genetic and biomarker-based approaches are both hindered in the identification of ecological microniches in microbial mats by their sampling requirements and spatial resolution. The community description of the OS and MS mats, as detailed above, is based on studies dealing with samples in the millimeter range. Similar resolutions have been typically employed in biomarker analysis of microbial mat systems. Sub-millimeter resolution has been achieved by slicing hypersaline or estuarine mats into 500 μm (Villanueva, del Campo, Guerrero, & Geyer, 2010) or 200 μm (Jonkers et al., 2003) thick slices and extracting the biomarkers from those slices. This approach enabled Villanueva et al. (2010) to generate intact polar lipid (IPL) and quinone depth profiles that revealed differences in microbial diversity and redox states. With such an approach, each slice yields a single data point, information on horizontal heterogeneity along these slices is thus averaged out. Because of this and because resolution is still low compared to the scales on which microbial networks function, these approaches are limited in their capacity to inform on the micrometer-scale organization of microbial mats and to target small differences in the biomarker signature related to specific niches or functions.

Mass Spectrometry Imaging (MSI) provides a 2D-image of the spatial distribution of a given target compound (biomarker) on a sample. An ionization probe rasters across the sample surface, and individual mass spectra are recorded at nm to μm -sized spots. Combined, these mass spectra reveal a map of molecular abundance (reviewed in Watrous & Dorrestein, 2011). Several ionization sources have been used in conjunction with different mass spectrometric systems for MSI, resulting in an array of techniques that diverge, for example, in the spatial and mass resolution of analysis, the molecules targeted, or the size of the analyzed sample (see Watrous & Dorrestein, 2011). Pioneering research on the suitability of MSI for microbial mats (e.g., Leefmann et al., 2013; Siljeström, Parenteau, Jahnke, & Cady, 2017) was carried out with Time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (ToF-SIMS). These studies demonstrated the ability of ToF-SIMS to ionize and detect organic molecules, as lipids and pigments, in such samples and were able to show that these molecules colocalized with microbial or microalgal cells.

Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization (MALDI) can be considered the most versatile approach to MSI, combining (a) high spatial resolution, though not capable of the nm-resolution potentially attainable by SIMS, (b) excellent mass resolution and sensitivity, especially when coupled to Fourier-transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FT-ICR-MS) that enables detection and proper identification of a large number of target compounds, (c) soft ionization that allows the analysis of large, intact molecules, and (d) the possibility to analyze large sample surfaces: up to several cm^2 , as opposed to the μm^2 regions common in ToF-SIMS measurements. Therefore, we hypothesize that MALDI FT-ICR MS-based MSI is ideally suited to reveal the nuances of spatial organization in microbial mats. The goal of this study was to trace the specific signatures of the different members of the chlorophototrophic community in the OS mat. This will help to obtain a better understanding of the spatial mat organization, including the existence of narrow ecological niches and their inhabitation by different functional groups, to reveal different ecotypes based on changes in biomarker composition and to identify new diagnostic markers for specific mat members under in situ conditions.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Study site and sample preparation

Microbial mat samples were collected in full sunlight on August 1st 2009, from the $\sim 65^\circ\text{C}$ outflow channel of OS, a slightly alkaline hot spring feature flowing into White Creek in the Lower Geyser Basin of Yellowstone National Park, Wyoming (USA). Samples were collected as push cores in 50-mL Falcon tubes, placed in a cooler in the dark, and frozen once returned to the camp. Samples were stored frozen at -20°C until further processing in 2018.

One sample was separated into three parts for bulk, conventional biomarker analysis. Vertical intervals were subsampled with a clean razor blade parallel to the mat surface and according to color and texture: green subsample (0–2 mm), red subsample 1 (2–8 mm, light red, and finely structured), red subsample 2 (8–11 mm, dark red), the latter one extended to the substratum. The three subsamples were freeze-dried and extracted according to a modified Bligh and Dyer method (Bligh & Dyer, 1959; Wörmer, Lipp, & Hinrichs, 2017): Samples were ultrasonicated and extracted into a solvent mixture (v:v) of methanol (MeOH), dichloromethane (DCM), and aqueous buffer (2:1:0.8). A phosphate buffer (8.7 g/L KH_2PO_4 , pH 7.4) and a trichloroacetic acid buffer (50 g/L, pH 2) were each used twice. The sonicated sediment was centrifuged, the supernatants were combined in a separatory funnel, and DCM and milliQ water were added for phase separation. After transferring the organic phase, the aqueous phase was extracted three more times with DCM. Pooled organic layers were then washed three times with milliQ water. The final extract was dried under a gentle stream of nitrogen and stored at -20°C . One gram of combusted sand was added to each sample to facilitate extraction.

TABLE 1 Biomarker nomenclature, including abbreviations (in bold)

Chloropigments			
Macrocycle structure	Modifications ^a	Esterifying alcohol ^a	Example
Chl , chlorophyll	m , one or more additional	iso , isoprenoidal	mBPheo c-non-iso
Pheo , pheophytin	methylations	non-iso , non-isoprenoidal	
Pyropheo , pyropheophytin		phytol	
BChl , bacteriochlorophyll		gg , geranyl-geraniol	
BPheo , bacteriopheophytin			
BPyropheo , bacteriopyropheophytin			
Quinones			
Type	Number of isoprenoidal units (n) and of unsaturations in the isoprenoidal chain (m) ^b		Example
CQ , chlorobiumquinone	n:m		MK_{10:10}
phyloq , phylloquinone			
MK , menaquinone			
PQ , plastoquinone			
UQ , ubiquinone			
IPLs			
Headgroup	Core structure	Sum of C atoms (C) and unsaturations (m) in the two aliphatic chains	Example
1G , monoglycosyl	AEG , acyl/alkylglycerol	C:m	PC-DAG_{42:0}
2G , diglycosyl	DAG , diacylglycerol		
BL , betaine	DEG , dialkylglycerol		
PC , phosphatidylcholine	Cer , ceramide		
PE , phosphatidylethanolamine			
PG , phosphatidylglycerol			
PI , phosphatidylinositol			
PME , phosphatidyl-N-methylethanolamine			
SQ , sulfoquinovosyl			
TM-OL , trimethyl ornithine lipid ^c			

^aApplicable to BChl c and BPheo c.

^bNot applicable to phyloq.

^cRefers to a specific lipid type, not to a headgroup.

Another sample of the intact mat was embedded in a gelatin (5%), carboxymethylcellulose (2%) mixture as described for marine sediments by Alfken et al. (2019). The embedding process was conducted stepwise: A base of embedding media was poured into a rectangular silicone mold and allowed to harden out, before the thawed mat was placed on top of it. Subsequently, small portions of liquid embedding medium were poured and allowed to diffuse into the mat and to cool to room temperature, until the mat was completely embedded (Figure 1a).

The embedded sample was stored frozen (−20°C) until sectioning into 100-micrometer slices on a Leica CM1950 cryomicrotome. Slicing provides a thin sample and an even surface, both beneficial for analysis (Alfken et al., 2019). Slices were transferred to indium tin oxide-coated glass slides (ITO slides, Bruker Daltonik) and adhered to them by warming the back of the ITO slide. After completely drying, referencing points were marked on the glass slide using a white correction pen and a high-resolution picture of the mat slice was taken. Slides were stored under vacuum, and elemental mapping and MSI performed on them within less than 72 hr.

2.2 | Conventional biomarker analysis

Molecular biomarkers in the sub-sectioned microbial mat extracts were analyzed by HPLC-MS on a maXis quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonik) equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source and coupled to a Dionex Ultimate 3000RS UHPLC. Bacterial IPLs were chromatographically separated by hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography on a Acquity BEH Amide 1.7 μm column, chloropigments and quinones by reversed phase chromatography on a Waters Acquity BEH C18 column (Wörmer et al., 2017; Wörmer, Lipp, Schröder, & Hinrichs, 2013). Mass spectrometric detection of biomarkers was carried out in positive ionization mode while scanning a mass to charge (*m/z*) range from 150 to 2000. MS2 scans were obtained in data-dependent mode. Compounds were identified according to exact precursor *m/z*, retention time, and fragmentation patterns. To provide semiquantitative information, peak areas were normalized by comparison to an internal standard (1,2-dihenearachidoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine, PC-DAG_{42:0}, Avanti Lipids) added during extraction. Normalized peak areas are expressed in the

result section as relative abundances, that is, fractions of the sum of all compounds detected in a certain compound class (pigments, quinones, and IPLs). See Table 1 for an explanation on biomarker nomenclature including abbreviations and Appendix S1 (supporting method description) for more details on the identification of bacteriochlorophyll *c* species. For IPLs, response factors were obtained by measurement of commercially available standard solutions of the most abundant lipid classes (Table S1). For all other compounds, a response factor of 1 was assumed.

2.3 | Elemental mapping

Elemental mapping of the OS mat slice was performed on a M4 Tornado system (Bruker Nano Analytics) equipped with a micro-focused Rh source (50 kV, 600 μ A) with a poly-capillary optic (25- μ m spot size). Measurements were conducted under vacuum, with a resolution of 25 μ m, 3 scans per spot, and a scan time of 3 ms per scan. The analysis of the complete microbial mat resulted in a mapped area of 11.0 x 20.7 mm. Data were initially processed and visualized with M4 Tornado Software version 1.3. The xy-matrix of Fe abundance was afterward imported into Matlab (R2016b) and overlaid on a high-resolution picture of the mat slice by referencing three teaching points.

2.4 | Mass spectrometry imaging of molecular biomarkers

To improve ionization of target compounds, an artificial matrix (2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid, DHB) was applied to the mat slice before analysis. Sublimation was chosen as application method, as it minimizes lateral heterogeneity of matrix during deposition (Murphy, Hankin, Barkley, & Berry, 2011). We followed a protocol provided by Bruker Daltonik: 100 mg of DHB was dissolved in 1 ml of acetone, and the resulting solution was evenly distributed on the bottom of a glass chamber heated to 120°C in a sand bath. The sample slide was taped at the outer bottom of a second inner glass chamber filled with ice. By creating a vacuum of 0.2 mbar in the space between inner and outer chamber, sublimation of the matrix onto the slide was started and carried out for 30 min.

Immediately after matrix application, MSI was performed with a 7T solariX XR FT-ICR-MS coupled to a MALDI source equipped with a Smartbeam II laser (Bruker Daltonik). Two measurement regions were defined in FlexImaging (Bruker Daltonik): a larger one targeting the complete mat until the substratum was measured with 75- μ m resolution, and a smaller one targeting only the green, upper part with 25- μ m resolution (Figure 1b). Of 7855 spots were analyzed for the larger area and 3962 for the smaller one. Laser settings were optimized for highest intensities with final settings being 35% of maximum laser power, 250 shots acquired per spot, and a frequency of 500 Hz. Laser spot size was set to small for

the 25- μ m analysis and to medium for the 75- μ m analysis to avoid overlapping spots.

For each spot, a mass spectrum was acquired in positive mode, with a data size of 1MW. To enhance sensitivity, CASI (continuous accumulation of selected ions) mode for the *m/z* range 600–1,000 was selected. A 25% data reduction was applied directly during acquisition, to avoid storing low-intensity noise signals. External mass calibration of the FT-ICR-MS system was performed in ESI mode with sodium trifluoroacetate. Internal lock mass calibration of each MSI spectrum was performed after acquisition with a DHB peak (4M-H₄ + 5Na, *m/z* 727.0234), as this compound was abundant throughout the entire mat. An example of a single mass spectrum is provided in Figure S1.

After calibration, *m/z*, intensity, and signal-to-noise ratio of all peaks in the *m/z* ranges relevant to IPLs, chloropigments, and quinones were exported together with their xy-coordinates for further processing in Matlab (R2016b). Export and calibration were performed with DataAnalysis (Bruker Daltonik).

In Matlab, each spectrum was searched for the targeted biomarkers by looking for their exact *m/z* (± 0.005 or ± 0.01). The list of compounds to be targeted was established based on their detection by the conventional, extraction-based approach. In the case of IPLs, given the wealth of lipid species, only the most abundant representatives of each lipid class were selected. A dominance of demetallized (bacterio)pheophytins over intact chlorophylls was observed in both the conventional and MSI analysis. (Bacterio)pheophytins are known to contribute to photosynthesis as electron acceptors (e.g., Klimov, Klevanik, Shuvalov, & Krasnovsky, 1977; Tokita, Hirota, Frigaard, Shimada, & Matsuura, 1999). However, the release of the central Mg ion is also a phenomenon encountered in the early stages of (bacterio)chlorophyll degradation in the environment, and during analysis, for example, by acidification during extraction, or by MALDI, especially when using proton-transfer matrices (Calvano, Ventura, Cataldi, & Palmisano, 2015; Vieler, Wilhelm, Goss, Süß, & Schiller, 2007). We therefore assumed pheophytinization takes place during sample analysis and, accordingly, exclusively targeted (bacterio)pheophytins in MSI, and interpreted their spatial distribution as analogous to their intact (bacterio)chlorophyll counterparts, indicative of active phototrophic communities.

A total of 16 chloropigment, 12 quinone, and 73 IPL species were targeted (Table S2). MSI yielded informative distribution maps for 64 of these 101 compounds. Distribution of these compounds, or the sums of several compounds, was plotted as colormaps with a color scale ranging from 0 to the 95th quantile, unless noted otherwise. Changes in abundance can be either due to an increase in the biological source of a particular biomarker or an increase in cellular concentration of the biomarker. To visualize contrasting or overlapping distributions of different biomarkers, their intensities were normalized to the 95th quantile, then the difference between these normalized intensities was calculated for each spot and plotted as a colormap. Compounds presented in the main text are representative of the corresponding compound class. Additional abundance maps are provided as Figures S2–S9.

TABLE 2 Selection of potentially relevant oxygenic (*Synechococcus* spp.) and anoxygenic chlorophototrophs in the OS microbial mat community and putative diagnostic biomarkers

Phylum	Species	Predicted lifestyle (Tank et al., 2017)	IPLs	Quinones	Chloropigments	References
Cyanobacteria	<i>Synechococcus</i> spp.	Aerobe, autotroph	1G-DAG, 2G-DAG, SQ-DAG, PG-DAG	PQ _{9,9'} , phylloq, OH-phylloq**	Chl <i>a</i>	Collins & Jones, (1981); Kilian et al., (2007); Wada & Murata, (1998); Ward, Panke, Kloppel, Christ, & Fredrickson, (1994)
Chloroflexi	<i>Chloroflexus</i> spp.	Anaerobe, oxygen-tolerant, autotroph, mixotroph	1G-DAG, 2G-DAG, PG-DAG, PI-DAG	MK _{8,8'} , MK _{10:10}	BChl <i>a</i> (minor), BChl <i>c</i> (major)	Fages, Griebenow, Griebenow, Holzwarth, & Schaffner, (1990); Hale, Blankenship, & Fuller, (1983); Knudsen, Jantzen, Bryn, Ormerod, & Sirevåg, (1982); Pierson & Castenholz, (1974); Ward et al., (1994)
	<i>Roseiflexus</i> spp.	Anaerobe, oxygen-tolerant, mixotroph	n.i.	MK _{11:11}	BChl <i>a</i>	Hanada, Takaichi, Matsuura, & Nakamura, (2002); van der Meer et al., (2010)
	<i>Ca. Roseilinea gracile</i> (uncultured)	Unknown	n.i.	n.i.	BChl <i>a</i> *	Klatt et al., (2011)
	<i>Ca. Chloranaerofilum corporosum</i> (uncultured)	Anaerobe	n.i.	MK _{10:10} **	BChl <i>a</i> (minor), BChl <i>c</i> (major)***	Keppen, Tourova, Kuznetsov, Ivanovsky, & Gorlenko, (2000); Taisova, Keppen, Lukashov, Arutyunyan, & Fetisova, (2002); Tank et al., (2017)
Acidobacteria	<i>Chloracidobacterium thermophilum</i>	Microaerophile, heterotroph	BL, PE-DAG, PME-DAG	MK _{8,7}	BChl <i>a</i> (minor), mBChl <i>c</i> (major)	Bryant et al., (2007); García Costas et al., (2012)
Chlorobi	<i>Ca. Thermochlorobacter aerophilum</i> (uncultured)	Aerobe, heterotroph	n.i.	n.i.	BChl <i>a</i> , BChl <i>d</i> **	Frigaard, Takaichi, Hirota, Shimada, & Matsuura, (1997); Hiraishi, (1999); Liu et al., (2012)

Listed biomarkers are based on isolated representatives or closely related strains, are predicted from genomes (*), or are inferred from distantly related strains (**).

Abbreviations for IPLs: BL, betaine lipid; DAG, diacylglycerol; G, glycosyl; PE, phosphatidylethanolamine; PG, phosphatidylglycerol; PI, phosphatidylinositol; PME, phosphatidyl-N-methylethanolamine; SQ, sulfoquinovosyl. Abbreviations for quinones: CQ, chlorobiumquinone; PQ_{9,9'}, plastoquinone; phylloq, phyloquinone; MK_{10:10}, menaquinone; n, number of isoprenoid units; m, number of unsaturations in the isoprenoid chain. Abbreviations for chloropigments: Chl, chlorophyll; BChl, bacteriochlorophyll; mBChl highly methylated bacteriochlorophyll. n.i., not investigated.

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 | Conventional biomarker analysis

In order to obtain a broad description of the chemotaxonomic composition of the mat, but also to inform MSI on potential target compounds, conventional analysis of chloropigments, quinones, and IPLs was performed on three mat subsamples characterized by differences in color and texture (Figure 2). Potential source organisms for the detected biomarkers are summarized in Table 2 together with relevant references.

The uppermost, green subsample was characterized by a dominance of chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) and associated pheophytin *a* (Pheo *a*), which accounted for 67% of the chloropigments (Figure 2a). Paired with the high abundance of plastoquinone (PQ) and phyloquinones (Figure 2b), of mono- and diglycosidic lipids with diacylglycerol cores (1G, 2G-DAG) and of sulfoquinovosyl diacylglycerols (SQ-DAGs) (Figure 2c), the biomarker profile is indicative of the predominance of oxygenic photoautotrophs, namely *Synechococcus* spp. (see Table 2). The presence of phyllo- and plastoquinones and to a lesser degree Chl *a* and Pheo *a*, throughout the red undermat may point to additional cyanobacterial populations inherited from former surface layers.

Menaquinones (MK), bacteriochlorophylls (BChl), and bacterio-pheophytins (BPheo) are indicative of anoxygenic phototrophs (see Table 2) and were detected in the green and the two reddish undermat subsamples (Figure 2). In the green subsample, the MK pool was dominated by MK_{11:11}. Relative abundance of BChl and BPheo was low in this sample, but highest for BPheo *a* and highly methylated BPheo *c* esterified to non-isoprenoidal alcohols, which each contributed 7% to the chloropigment pool. Both MK_{11:11} and BPheo *a* suggest a relatively high contribution from *Roseiflexus* spp. in the green part of the mat, which is consistent with its identification by genetic and genomic techniques (Klatt et al., 2011; Ross et al., 2012; Thiel et al., 2017).

In the two subsamples from the reddish undermat, the relative abundance of BPheo *c* strongly increased compared to the green subsample (from 7 to 51 and 63%, respectively). These compounds can be related to a higher abundance of anoxygenic chlorophototrophs different from *Roseiflexus* spp. (see Table 2). Low methylation species (equivalent to the 8-Et, 12-Me BChl *c* characteristic for *Chloroflexus aurantiacus*) with esterified phytyl, geranylgeranyl, or octadecanyl alcohols mimic the BChl *c* signature of *Cfx. aurantiacus* (Fages, Griebenow, Griebenow, Holzwarth, & Schaffner, 1990). BChl *c* with higher degrees of methylation has been described in *Cab. thermophilum* (García Costas et al., 2012). Notably, in the OS mat these compounds often exhibit esterification with non-isoprenoidal alcohols (C₁₆, C₁₇, and C₁₈), which was also observed in *Cab. thermophilum* (García Costas et al., 2012). Abundance of BPheo *a* species increases in the undermat and may represent a mixed signal of *Roseiflexus* spp. and other phototrophs in which it is present as a minor pigment (e.g., *Chloroflexus* spp., *Cab. thermophilum*, or “*Ca. T. aerophilum*,” see Table 2).

Compared to the green subsample, specific quinone species, most prominently ubiquinones and MK_{10:10}, showed a higher abundance in samples from the undermat. MK_{10:10} may well represent *Chloroflexus* spp. (see Table 2), which would be in agreement with the BPheo *c* signature described above. Ubiquinones were abundant in the upper red sample, most likely representing aerobic respiration (Hiraishi, 1999). MK_{8:7}, as putative biomarker for *Cab. thermophilum* (see Table 2), was present in low and roughly constant relative abundances in the different subsamples.

Regarding IPL signatures, the lack of reference profiles for several anoxygenic chlorophototrophs (Table 2) and the apparent similarity between IPLs from *Cfx. aurantiacus* (Imhoff & Bias-Imhoff, 1995; Ward, Panke, Kloppel, Christ, & Fredrickson, 1994) and *Synechococcus* spp. complicate interpretation. As already mentioned, the green subsample was enriched in IPLs that are consistent with a cyanobacterial dominance, and these IPLs extended throughout the deeper samples. However, their relative abundances decrease in the undermat, as mono- and diglycosidic lipids with ether-linked core lipids (1G, 2G-DEG) become dominant. The contribution of these lipids increased from 36% in the green to 50 and 64% in the red mat sections. Trimethylated ornithine lipids (TM-OL) also strongly increase and turn into relevant contributors to the IPL pool in the undermat. Betaine lipids and phospholipids remain minor contributors, but their relative abundances increase in the deeper parts. Both lipid classes have been reported for *Cab. thermophilum* (García Costas et al., 2012).

The wealth of G-DEGs and TM-OLs in the undermat suggests that they originate from organisms that are especially abundant in these deeper layers, including anoxygenic phototrophs of the phylum Chloroflexi. These have been described to dominate the undermat (e.g., Thiel et al., 2016) and are also identified by our pigment and quinone data. While TM-OLs are absent from published IPL profiles of *Cfx. aurantiacus* (Table 2), these studies agree on the dominance of glycolipids: 1G-DAG and 2G-DAG. However, they do not report glycolipids with DEG core structures. Actually, to our knowledge, bacterial DEGs with glycosidic headgroups have not been described in cultures so far, but have been encountered in streamer biofilms from the YNP (Schubotz et al., 2013) and alkaline deep-sea hydrothermal vents (Bradley, Fredricks, Hinrichs, & Summons, 2009), and assigned to unknown thermophilic bacteria. Based on the present data, we suggest that 1G-DEG and 2G-DEG could be main constituents of thermophilic Chloroflexi membranes. This hypothesis will be further explored by evaluating the colocalization of these IPL species with specific markers for Chloroflexi by MSI.

3.2 | Elemental mapping

While elemental mapping of the sliced mat informs on the distribution of a suite of elements, in the present study we concentrated on Fe, which shows a prominent band of increased abundance at a depth of ~ 5 mm (Figure 1). This feature is consistent with the transition from anoxic to oxic conditions (oxic-anoxic transition zone,

FIGURE 2 Biomarker distributions in lipid extracts from three subsamples of the Octopus Spring microbial mat. Subsampling was performed based on characteristic color and texture: green subsample (0–2 mm), red subsample 1 (2–8 mm, light red and finely structured), and red subsample 2 (8–11 mm, dark red)

OATZ) resulting in the precipitation of Fe. The significant distance between the upper green part of the mat and the OATZ demonstrates the existence of a ~ 3 mm deep area, below the main zone of oxygenic phototrophy, in which oxygen is available during the day. Location of the OATZ, as described here, is consistent with microelectrode measurements (Jensen, Steunou, Bhaya, Kuhl, & Grossman, 2011; Revsbech & Ward, 1984) and with the presence of aerobic and microaerobic organisms detected in the MS undermat (Thiel et al., 2016). Below the OATZ, anoxic conditions are expected to persist throughout the day.

3.3 | Mass spectrometry imaging

3.3.1 | Zonation of the chlorophototroph community in the OS microbial mat

To provide a description of the general structure of the OS microbial mats, we first targeted a ~ 1 cm × 0.5 cm section of the mat with 75- μ m resolution. The chlorophototrophs dominating the OS mats rely on specific chlorophylls and bacteriochlorophylls for light harvesting (Table 2). Based on the distribution of Pheo and BPheo, and supported by colocalization of different quinone species, we observed a spatially structured system that allowed identification of major functional groups of chlorophototrophs (Figures 3, 4). The first group, formed by *Synechococcus* spp., was identified by the presence of Pheo *a*. *Synechococcus* spp. concentrates in three areas, most prominently in the upper 2 mm, but also in the undermat: in a second layer located at the putative OATZ and finally in several layers spreading horizontally and vertically at a depth below 6 mm (Figure 3). The latter two populations are consistent with the presence of *Synechococcus* spp. in the metagenomic analysis of the MS undermat (Thiel et al., 2016). Comparison to complementary biomarkers can contribute to the question whether these signatures are inherited from former surface layers gradually losing activity or are

indicative of active populations, adapted to the specific conditions in the undermat.

As expected, PQ_{9,9} as the major quinone in cyanobacteria localizes with Pheo *a* in the surface layer. It is, however, practically absent below the OATZ. The increased relative abundance of PQ_{9,9} compared to Pheo *a* in the upper layer might indicate an increase of PQ_{9,9} over Chl *a* production in high-light, oxic environments. Kilian et al. (2007) investigated the response of a *Synechococcus* strain isolated from OS to increasing light irradiances and observed reduced levels of Chl *a* and phycobilisomes. At the same time, the concentration of carotenoids and the transcription of genes encoding tocopherol cyclase increased. We hypothesize that similar to tocopherol and carotenoids, PQ_{9,9} might be acting as an antioxidant that buffers the impact of reactive oxygen species generated through excessive excitation of the photosynthetic apparatus in the upper parts of the mat exposed to full sunlight. A relative decrease of Pheo *a* concentration would aim at preventing the damage from excessive light absorption.

Lack of PQ_{9,9} in the deeper parts of the mat is, however, more likely to indicate a larger contribution of dead or inactive *Synechococcus* spp. cells, with a quicker degradation of PQ_{9,9} compared to Pheo *a*. Pyropheophytin *a* (Pyropheo *a*), a product of the anaerobic degradation of Chl *a* (Szymczak-Żyła, Kowalewska, & Louda, 2008), accumulates in proximity of the deeper *Synechococcus* layers, confirming the ongoing degradation of formerly active cyanobacterial populations. At the same time, its prominent occurrence at and especially below the tentatively established OATZ confirms oxygen depletion in these layers. A predominance of dead or dying cyanobacteria in the deeper undermat is consistent with the description of moribund cells and empty filaments (e.g., Doemel & Brock, 1977), with the observation that below 5 mm DNA was heavily degraded (Thiel et al., 2016) and with the need to balance continued growth of the mat with decomposition (Doemel & Brock, 1977).

The remaining mat is inhabited by anoxygenic chlorophototrophs producing several kinds of BPheo *a* and *c* (Figure 4) and MKs

FIGURE 3 Images of the mat slice (a) and 75- μ m resolution MSI of pheophytin *a*, PQ_{9,9}, and pyropheophytin *a* (b–d) depicting the spatial distribution of the oxygenic chlorophototroph *Synechococcus* spp. Please note the different scales of the color bar. Panel (e) shows the difference between normalized relative abundance of Pheo *a* and Pyropheo *a* (denoted as Δ Pheo *a*, Pyropheo *a*). The tentatively established OATZ is plotted as dashed grey line

FIGURE 4 Images of the mat slice and layers dominated by specific biomarker signals (a, d, g) and 75- μ m resolution MSI of bacteriopheophytin a (b), $MK_{11:11}$ (c), phytol esterified bacteriopheophytin c (e) and the sum of non-isoprenoidal highly methylated bacteriopheophytins (h) depicting the spatial distribution of the different groups of anoxygenic chlorophototrophs. Please note the different scales of the color bar. MSI of individual bacteriopheophytins, which have been grouped here (h), is presented as Figure S2. Panels (f) and (i) show the difference between normalized relative abundances of bacteriopheophytin a and the other bacteriopheophytins plotted (denoted as Δ compound 1, compound 2). The tentatively established OATZ is shown as dashed gray line. Distribution of the biomarker profiles attributed to different anoxygenic chlorophototrophs described in the text (IIa-e, red: *Roseiflexus* spp.; III, yellow: *Chloroflexus* spp.; IV, blue: *Cab. thermophilum*) is superimposed on the mat image

FIGURE 5 Images of the mat slice and layers dominated by specific biomarker signals (a) and 75- μ m resolution MSI of selected menaquinones (b-e). Please note the different scales of the color bar. As the 95th quantile for $MK_{8:7}$ was zero, the 99th quantile was chosen as the upper limit of the color scale, for all other plots the 95th quantile was chosen. Distribution of the biomarker profiles attributed to different anoxygenic chlorophototrophs described in the text (II-IV) is superimposed on the mat image

(Figure 5). Partial colocalization of some of these compounds suggests a certain degree of overlap, which is most notable around and just below the OATZ. Differences in relative abundance of biomarkers, together with some unique features, however, established a

zonation of preferential habitats of the anoxygenic chlorophototrophs (layers II-IV in Figures 4-6).

Roseiflexus spp. were identified by layers dominated by BPheo a and $MK_{11:11}$ (Table 2) and are very widely distributed, from the top

(layers IIa in Figures 4–6) to the very bottom of the mat (layers IIe in Figures 4–6). This distribution throughout the mat, above and below the OATZ, relates both to the metabolic plasticity (Hanada, Takaichi, Matsuura, & Nakamura, 2002; van der Meer et al., 2010) and the high microdiversity (Thiel et al., 2017; Thiel et al., 2016) of *Roseiflexus* spp. It is also consistent with the fact that *Roseiflexus* spp. has been described as the most abundant and active chlorophototroph in the upper MS undermat and to also be prevalent in the top green part of the mat (Klatt et al., 2013; Thiel et al., 2017). In Nakabusa spring mats, which are very similar to the OS and MS mats, *Roseiflexus* spp. was abundant throughout the ~ 5 mm analyzed and dominant from 3 to 5 mm depth in samples collected in summer (Martinez et al., 2019). “*Ca. Roseilinea gracile*” is also expected to exclusively produce BChl *a*; however, due to the lack of knowledge on additional specific biomarkers, we cannot assess its contribution to the observed BPheo *a* signal.

MSI revealed highly characteristic biomarker signatures in the different layers attributable to *Roseiflexus* spp. Layers IIa and IIb, located in the oxic, high-light environment, present decreased BPheo *a* signals, which can be interpreted as a strategy aimed at preventing the damage from excessive light absorption. Two abundant BPheo *a* layers (IIc and IId) were found around the OATZ, in a depth of 5 to 6 mm. Such increased abundance of BPheo *a* can point to a shift toward more intense light harvesting. Cultured members of *Roseiflexus* spp. are able of photoheterotrophic growth under anaerobic conditions in the light and chemoheterotrophic growth under aerobic conditions in the dark (Hanada et al., 2002; van der Meer et al., 2010). The OATZ provides a redox boundary layer that still receives substantial amounts of light in the absorption range of bacteriochlorophylls (Martinez et al., 2019) and may thus be a preferential habitat for phototrophic *Roseiflexus* spp..

At the OATZ (layer IIc) and above, BPheo *a* is accompanied by strong MK_{11:11} signals, while this quinone is less abundant below (layers IId and IIe). *Roseiflexus* spp. thus seem to require a larger pool of MK in order to thrive under oxic conditions. Possible explanations could point to changes in metabolic preferences as outlined above, reduced efficiency of the low redox-potential MKs in the presence of oxygen or to a strategy aimed at reducing oxidative stress. In Chlorobi, quinones play a quenching role, inhibiting energy transfer in chlorosomes under oxic conditions (Frigaard, Takaichi, Hirota, Shimada, & Matsuura, 1997; Wang, Brune, & Blankenship, 1990). Despite the differences between *Roseiflexus* and Chlorobi (e.g., the presence of chlorosomes), MK_{11:11} could play a similar role, preventing cellular damage in the oxic zone. The biomarker signature of *Roseiflexus* spp. thus clearly identifies the response of different ecotypes to changing oxygen and light concentrations, a change that, in the most dramatic example of layers IIc and IId, occurs in less than 400 μm.

It is also noteworthy that MK_{7:7} presents a spatial distribution highly similar to that of MK_{11:11} (Figure 5), with the exception of a slightly lower abundance in layer IIa. Based on the colocalization of both compounds, we suggest a common source, for example, *Roseiflexus* spp., even though to our knowledge, MK_{7:7} production

has not been described for this organism. Another potential source of MK_{7:7} could be the aerobic “*Ca. T. aerophilum*”. MK_{7:7} is a dominant quinone species in Chlorobi, together with chlorobiumquinone (ChQ) (Frigaard et al., 1997). However, as neither ChQ, nor BChl *d* or BPheo *d*, nor any farnesyl-esterified BChl or BPheo species (all of which are typically present in Chlorobi) were detected in the bulk analysis, we consider “*Ca. T. aerophilum*” a less likely option.

The anoxygenic phototrophic community presents some additional biomarker profiles that cannot be attributed to *Roseiflexus* spp. Several layers around 7 mm depth (layer III in Figures 4–6) are characterized by high abundance of low methylation BPheo *c*, primarily esterified to a phytol chain (Figure 4), and a dominance of MK_{10:10} (Figure 5). Given the similarity to the biomarker profile of *Cfx. aurantiacus* (Table 2), we assigned these layers to *Chloroflexus* spp.. *Chloroflexus* and *Roseiflexus* signatures present some overlap around the OATZ, but the former is clearly dominating in the deeper, anoxic undermat. An increased presence of *Chloroflexus* spp. in these layers can be explained by a better adaptation to low light, especially due to the presence of chlorosomes (Martinez et al., 2019; Oostergetel, van Amerongen, & Boekema, 2010). The minor contribution of *Chloroflexus* above the OATZ is consistent with relative abundance data based on amplicon sequence read abundance from Thiel et al. (2016) for the upper undermat (3–5 mm depth) of MS, where this genus accounted for ~ 1%. These authors did not analyze deeper layers, in which we observed a higher occurrence of *Chloroflexus*, as DNA was heavily degraded. While we agree that decomposition of formerly active phototrophic layers is the dominant process at this depth, expressed in the presence of Pyropheo *a* discussed above, we do not observe degradation of biomarkers for anoxygenic phototrophs. Moreover, the fact that biomarkers indicative of *Chloroflexus* are almost exclusive to this depth, contradicts the hypothesis of inherited signals.

Relative abundance of the *Chloroflexus* marker MK_{10:10} as opposed to MK_{11:11} attributed to *Roseiflexus*, does not significantly change above and below the OATZ. In their study evidencing fluorescence quenching by quinones in Chlorobi, Frigaard et al. (1997) also noted that this effect was much smaller in *Cfx. aurantiacus* and concluded that the energy transfer in these organisms under oxic conditions was regulated to a much smaller degree, if at all.

The BPheo *c* signature in layer III is more complex than observed for *Cfx. aurantiacus* (Fages et al., 1990; Pierson & Castenholz, 1974) and includes abundant highly methylated non-isoprenoidal BPheo *c* and smaller amounts of methylated isoprenoidal BPheo *c* (Figure 4, Figure S2). This might reflect the need to increase the yield of light harvesting by diversifying BChl *c* structures, but could also point to the presence of additional chlorophototrophic members, such as “*Ca. C. corporosum*.” Location in the deeper undermat would be consistent with the preference of “*Ca. C. corporosum*” for highly reducing environments. Furthermore, the presence of BPheo *a* and *c*, and MK_{10:10} coincides with biomarker signatures of the distantly related *Oscillochloris trichoides*, as well as with functional gene analysis (Taisova, Keppen, Lukashev, Arutyunyan, & Fetisova, 2002; Tank et al., 2017) and lend further support to “*Ca. C. corporosum*” as an additional source organism.

FIGURE 6 Images of the mat slice (a) and 75- μm resolution MSI of pheophytin *a* (b) and selected IPLs attributed to cyanobacterial layers (c–f). Picture of the mat slice superimposed with the groups of anoxygenic chlorophototrophs described above (g) and 75- μm resolution MSI of selected IPLs (h–l). IPL species are representative for their respective lipid classes

Another potential contributor to the BPheo *c* signature and more specifically to highly methylated BPheo *c* esterified to non-isoprenoidal alcohols would be *Cab. thermophilum*. High abundances of these compounds slightly above and at the OATZ (layer IV in Figure 4), where they colocalize with the weak MK_{8:7} signal (Figure 5), suggest the possibility that this might be a region harboring microaerophilic *Cab. thermophilum*.

Ubiquinones, which were abundant in the upper red layer according to bulk biomarker analysis, were not detected by MSI. Possible reasons are a more difficult ionization compared to menaquinones or sample heterogeneity, as our MSI approach only targets a limited area on a 100 μm thick slice.

3.3.2 | Assignment of IPL profiles to specific members of the chlorophototroph community

Images of IPL distributions confirm *Synechococcus* spp. layers as the main source of 1G-DAG, 2G-DAG, and SQ-DAG (Figure 6). Betaine lipids with diacylglycerol cores (BL-DAG) also accumulate around these cyanobacterial layers, although to our knowledge, they have not been reported in *Synechococcus* spp. and only once in a cyanobacterium (Rezanka, Viden, Go, Dor, & Dembitsky, 2003). While 1G-DAG, 2G-DAG, and SQ-DAG are considered typical lipids to be produced by cyanobacteria, their low abundance in other layers is striking, as glycolipids are considered canonical lipids of photosynthetic membranes and are believed to be main constituents of

Chloroflexi (e.g., Knudsen, Jantzen, Bryn, Ormerod, & Sirevåg, 1982; Mizoguchi, Harada, Yoshitomi, & Tamiaki, 2013; Ward et al., 1994).

Apparently, while maintaining glycosidic headgroups, the OS mat organisms rely on different ether-linked core lipids, such as 1G-DEG, 2G-DEG, and sulfoquinovosyl dialkylglycerols (SQ-DEG), but also on monoglycosidic lipids with mixed acyl/alkyl core lipids (1G-AEG). 1G-DEG virtually covers all layers attributed to anoxygenic chlorophototrophs but is especially abundant in the *Roseiflexus*-attributed layers IIc, d, and e. SQ-DEG and monounsaturated 2G-DEG accumulate in layers IIa and IIe, while being almost absent from the central mat piece. Diunsaturated 2G-DEG seems to slightly differ from this distribution, with increased abundance around layer IIc (Figure S3). 1G-AEG colocalizes with layers IIb and IIc. The different *Roseiflexus* layers thus present an impressive diversity of glycosidic IPLs with specific ether-linked core structures.

For layers III and IV, attributed to *Chloroflexus* spp. and *Cab. thermophilum*, respectively, no specific IPL biomarkers could be identified. Both layers harbor 1G-DEG, which we have postulated as a generic marker for anoxygenic chlorophototrophs in the present system, while only isolated spots of BL-DAG, described to be dominant in *Cab. thermophilum* (García Costas et al., 2012), are observed in layer IV.

TM-OL presents a quite unique distribution. Given its abundance in the chlorophototroph-devoid region between ~ 2 and 4 mm, we argue against assigning this lipid to anoxygenic chlorophototrophs, and instead suggest a chemoheterotrophic origin. OL, including TM-OL, has been previously detected in hot springs from the YNP, but

could not be assigned to any specific bacteria (Schubotz et al., 2015; Schubotz et al., 2013). Originally, TM-OL was described in planctomycetes (Moore et al., 2013). A chemoheterotrophic origin and a comparatively higher oxygen tolerance are suggested for phosphatidyl-N-methylethanolamine diacylglycerol (PME-DAG), which accumulates in the upper ~ 2 mm and is the only phospholipid detected by MSI (Figure S7). PME-DAG is widely distributed, and has, for example, been attributed to heterotrophic bacteria in inactive hydrothermal chimneys (Reeves et al., 2014) or in sediments from asphalt volcanos (Schubotz, Lipp, Elvert, & Hinrichs, 2011), but also to *Cab. thermophilum* (García Costas et al., 2012).

3.3.3 | Fine-scale distribution of chlorophototrophs in the upper, green mat layer

To obtain a more detailed description of the upper green part of the OS mat, we employed MSI at three-fold higher resolution. As expected, biomarkers attributed to *Synechococcus* spp. are conspicuous in this region. However, only the upper ~ 250 μm (area 1 in Figure 7) is dominated by oxygenic phototrophs. Below, and to some degree colocalizing with this layer, the distinctive signatures of anoxygenic photoautotrophs are abundant. *Roseiflexus* spp. biomarker signatures, including BPheo *a* and characteristic IPLs such as 1G-DEG, 2G-DEG and SQ-DEG, occupy a large part of the investigated region in a more dispersed distribution, slightly overlapping with the *Synechococcus* layer (area 2 in Figure 7). This overlap

is also confirmed by the spatial distribution of MK_{11:11} and PQ_{9:9}. Unfortunately, these were the only quinones detected. Difficulties in detecting the less abundant species were possibly caused by the small laser spots employed in this experiment, which resulted in lower ion yields. “*Ca. T. aerophilum*” may also contribute to the BPheo *a* signature overlapping the cyanobacterial layers, as this organism is expected to thrive in highly oxygenated environments and has been described to be closely associated to *Synechococcus* (Tank et al., 2017). However, the lack of diagnostic biomarkers prevents categorical identification.

Based on the 75- μm MSI results, we suggested a potential cyanobacterial origin for BL-DAG. The more detailed view provided here, however, shows that cyanobacterial and BL-DAG distributions are slightly offset against each other. When comparing relative abundances of 1G-DAG and BL-DAG (panel f in Figure 7), we observed that 1G-DAG dominance matches high Pheo *a* regions, while BL-DAG dominates in the surrounding areas. MSI therefore identifies BL-DAG as originating from microbial players with close spatial association to *Synechococcus* spp., but not directly from a cyanobacterial signal. A strong colocalization of BL-DAG and PME-DAG (Figure S9) suggests a common source for these two lipid classes, which could include chemoheterotrophic organisms, but also *Cab. thermophilum*, with a lipid profile dominated by these two species (García Costas et al., 2012; Sinnighe Damsté et al., 2014). However, the microaerophilic character of *Cab. thermophilum* and the spatial offset between diagnostic lipids and pigments prevent a clear assignment.

FIGURE 7 Magnification images of the mat slice (a, g, m) and 25- μm resolution MSI of selected biomarkers and of the difference between normalized relative abundances of selected biomarkers (denoted as Δ compound 1, compound 2). MSI of individual biomarkers, which are grouped or plotted as differences here, is presented as Figure S4. Color scale ranges from the 5th to the 95th quantile for individual compounds and between -0.75 and 0.75 for differences between relative abundances. Distribution of the different regions of chlorophototrophs (1, blue: *Synechococcus* spp.; 2, red: *Roseiflexus* spp., 3a, yellow: *Cab. thermophilum*, 3b, yellow: *Chloroflexus* spp.) in the green layer is superimposed on the mat images

Phytol esterified BPheo *c* and highly methylated BPheo *c* esterified to non-isoprenoidal alcohols are abundant along filaments at the bottom of, and immediately below, the *Synechococcus-Roseiflexus* layer. We assigned them to *Chloroflexus* spp. and *Cab. thermophilum*. Based on the relative abundance of these two types of BPheo *c*, *Chloroflexus* spp. is more likely to be located slightly deeper (layer 3b in Figure 7) than *Cab. thermophilum* (layer 3a in Figure 7). Abundance of BPheo *a* at these same layers might be explained by a decrease of the Bchl *c/a* ratio under high-light conditions, as observed for *Cfx. aurantiacus* (Pierson & Castenholz, 1974). Interestingly, these signals strongly colocalize with 2G-AEG_{35:0} (Figure 7), for which no prior sources are known.

3.3.4 | Fine-scale adjustments of cyanobacterial membrane lipid composition

The high resolution of MSI allows to evaluate specific adjustments in the biomarker pool of a seemingly homogeneous layer. In this case, we focused on the distribution of individual species of 1G-DAG in the *Synechococcus* spp. dominated layer (area 1 in Figures 7 and 8). Fine-scale MSI revealed that monounsaturated species are localized slightly above their completely saturated counterparts and thus seem to form the first barrier of light exposure (Figure 8). On a scale of ~ 200 μ m, the cyanobacterial community finely adjusts its membrane composition, selectively synthesizing monounsaturated over saturated species to deal with prevailing environmental conditions. Gombos et al. (1997) reported that an increase in the unsaturation of membrane lipids in *Synechococcus* sp. PCC7942 enhanced the tolerance of the cyanobacterium to high light. More recently, the existence of putative *Synechococcus* spp. ecotypes vertically distributed along the uppermost MS green layer has been postulated (Becraft et al., 2015). Interestingly, these putative ecotypes present different responses to light, with strains representative of surface ecotypes growing faster under high light (Nowack et al., 2015). Our MSI data, retrieved from a naturally growing community at high spatial resolution, suggest that these putative ecotypes present lipid compositions finely adjusted to the light niches they are occupying.

4 | CONCLUSIONS

Recent investigations of microbial mats have been largely driven by analytical developments and have witnessed the revolution enabled by microsensors and molecular genetic techniques (Bolhuis et al., 2014 and references therein). In the present study, the use of a novel approach, whole mat MSI of molecular biomarkers enabled by MALDI FT-ICR MS, affords a new look on the Octopus Spring microbial mat, and on the fine-tuned sequence of chlorophototrophs with unique biomarker signatures that populate the mat (Figure 9).

Synechococcus spp. dominates the upper ~ 250 μ m of the green surface layer. Inside this layer, a fine-scale adjustment of the cyanobacterial population to high light is evidenced in the unsaturation pattern of glycolipids. Cyanobacteria directly exposed to high-light conditions present membranes enriched in monounsaturated species. Below this first barrier, the relative amount of completely saturated cyanobacterial membrane lipids grows. With increasing depth, biomarker signatures attributed to *Roseiflexus* spp., *Cab. thermophilum*, and *Chloroflexus* spp. are all encountered in the top mm of the microbial mat. While *Roseiflexus* and *Synechococcus* biomarker overlap to a certain degree, the chlorosome containing *Cab. thermophilum* and *Chloroflexus* spp. is located in deeper, lower light microenvironments. BL-DAG and PME-DAG are abundant and localized in close proximity to cyanobacterial markers. Their producers remain to be identified but are most likely linked to chemo- or photoheterotrophy.

Phototrophic activity extends beyond this green layer, with *Roseiflexus* spp. clearly dominating the upper undermat. In the lower undermat, *Chloroflexus* spp. seems to become increasingly abundant. The transition from oxic to anoxic conditions is identified as a region where chemical signatures of anoxygenic phototrophs accumulate, dominated by *Roseiflexus* spp., but partaken by a suite of organisms. Micrometer-scale adjustments in the biomarker signature of *Roseiflexus* spp. are especially notable in this region and are consistent with the existence of different ecotypes carrying out specific metabolic strategies or adapting to redox conditions. Through colocalization with diagnostic quinone and pigment biomarkers, glycosidic dietherlipids are proposed as major constituents of the membranes of these anoxygenic chlorophototrophs.

FIGURE 8 Magnification image of the mat slice superimposed with the distribution of the *Synechococcus* dominated region 1 (a, d), 25- μ m resolution MSI of saturated and monounsaturated 1G-DAG species (b, c) and of the difference between normalized relative abundances of these biomarkers (denoted as Δ compound 1, compound 2)

FIGURE 9 Summary of the microscale organization and main biomarker signatures in the OS microbial mat. Changing font size of BPheo a, MK_{11:11} and MK_{7:7} represents changing relative abundances above and below the OATZ

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section.

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